

Sonification and Clustering: a Multi-Sensory Perspective for Precision Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Melodies are sequences of pitches distributed over time. In medicine, clinical variables, measured at regular intervals, can also be treated as quantities distributed over time. Thus, they can be mapped to sounds, creating melodies. These sonified trajectories can provide a multi-sensory perspective on disease progress for a sample of patients. Musical similarity becomes a tool to group patients with similar disease progress. Here, we focus on diabetic kidney disease (DKD) patients, proposing a sonification of their filtering efficiency information (through eGFR). We obtain Hertz for pitches and spectral centroids. Then, we use this information to build clusters of patients. We adopt a statistics method based on curve-parameter similarity (*Traj*), and then we propose a technique based on Fourier coefficients for symbolic-music analysis. We compare clusters built upon original values and Hertz, gaining hints on information found via proposed sonification. Possible future developments point to deeper connections between music theory, computer science, statistics, and precision medicine.

Keywords: diabetic kidney disease, eGFR, sonification, Fourier coefficients

1. INTRODUCTION

Sonification [1, 2] is the art (and science) of mapping data to sound. According to [1], “Sonification is the use of non-speech audio to convey information or perceptualize data.” It allows for a multi-sensory perspective on different phenomena, potentially catching hidden or hard-to-find information. Recent examples of its use in the medical domain involve sonification of the Covid genome [3]; enhanced information detection from medical imagery [4]; 3-dimensional representation of the human brain [5]. Sonification can also enter the domain of precision medicine. In this branch of medicine, the heterogeneity of patients is specifically taken into account, aiming to find the best individualized therapeutic strategies according to personal characteristics. It is the overturning of the “one-model-fits-all” paradigm.

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Several diseases require the observation of patients across a certain period. Longitudinal datasets contain the information of patients that are observed at different data points. Analyzing the variation of some information through time means that patients are characterized by longitudinal trajectories of a variable (or more variables). It is possible to cluster patients according to their path similarity. This approach is particularly relevant to finding patterns of behavior, and finding how subgroups of similar patients responded to the treatment. Such an approach aiming to foster individualized therapeutic strategies is crucial for a disease characterized by a high degree of heterogeneity, such as type-2 diabetic complications.

Let us focus on diabetic kidney disease (DKD). Patients with DKD are mainly monitored according to their estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) over time, a measure of kidney filtering efficiency. The information represented by eGFR trajectories can be mapped into sound. Thus, the temporal information of each patient can become a melody.

In this research, we sonify trajectories of kidney-filtering efficiency, using this information to build clusters of similarly-behaving patients. There are existing approaches to sound-information clustering [6]; however, here we focus on symbolic content first derived as MIDI information and then mapped to Hertz values.

We consider a dataset of 256 DKD patients. We cluster them according to the *Traj* method, based on curve parameters comparison [7]. *Traj* has already been used to cluster diabetic patients according to their time evolution of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) [8]. We compare the patients’ grouping obtained with original data and with the sonified ones. We also express comments according to their age, mapped to spectral centroids of sound. In fact, timbre can help differentiate amongst people with similar eGFR path but with different age ranges. Finally, we sketch a new method of clustering, based on Fourier coefficients and derived from mathematical music theory [9], to be used in future research.

Our article is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes the proposed sonification strategy, the *Traj* clustering technique, and the proposed Fourier-based strategy. Section 3 presents the first sonification outputs and the clusters’ comparisons. Finally, section 4 ends the article with discussion and conclusions.

2. DATASET AND METHODS

2.1 The Dataset

In a preliminary study, we sonified the eGFR trajectories of 10 DKD patients, comparing clustering results based on original data and on derived ones [10]. Here, we focus on 256 patients, allowing the application of different clustering techniques (section 2.3). The longitudinal dataset contains information on demographic and clinical variables, characterizing disease evolution over time, diabetes-related pathologies, and family history of disease for each patient. We focus on eGFR and age.

The dataset has been accessed during a project funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Action RIA Research and Innovation action Call: H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020; Topic: SC1-BHC-02-2019.

2.2 The Sonification Strategy

In this section, we describe the considered sonification technique. We mainly focus on the pitch. To enrich our analysis, we also consider timbre to distinguish between people of different ages: The higher the age, the lower the overall harmonic component. For each patient, we can thus consider the spectral centroid in addition to melodies. The sonified dataset will thus contain 256 arrays (melodies) with a sequence of pitches as a MIDI number and Hertz, jointly with an indication of spectral centroid to characterize timbres. The idea is to join symbolic and sound information.

The technique to obtain notes is the following.

We first start with the array of values of eGFR. We consider four measurements, taken yearly. Thus, the time distance between two consecutive measurements is the same, and in our musical rendition, there are no rhythmical variations. The one-year difference, in our mapping, becomes a quarter-note rhythmic distance in a 4/4 tempo. For each patient, we obtain a four-note melody at regular time intervals. We develop a 3-step procedure:

- trajectory rescaling between 0 and 1;
- values rescaling in a chosen MIDI interval;
- final mapping to Hertz.

Let us describe each step in detail.

Values of eGFR are measured in mL/min/1.73m². The maximum possible value is 100, while the threshold value for sufficient kidney efficiency is 60. Measurements of eGFR comprised between 15 and 29 denote a severe loss of kidney function, and, below 15, kidney failure¹. In the considered dataset, there are no patients with kidney failure. Thus, in our analysis, we first choose 100 as the max, and 20 as the minimum, rescaling eGFR values to numbers strictly comprised between 0 and 1:

$$x = (eGFR - 20)/(100 - 20) \quad (1)$$

The second step involves a rescaling to obtain MIDI pitch note numbers in a range approximately between 49 (C#3)

¹<https://kdigo.org/>

and 72 (C5), that is, in two octaves playable by several musical instruments and the human voice. This choice constitutes a good mapping because the resulting notes are within our central hearing range.

$$y = f(x) = x * 23 + 49. \quad (2)$$

The results are rounded to natural numbers. Finally, the third and last passage is a mapping from MIDI to frequencies in Hertz:

$$z = g(y) = 2^{\left(\frac{y-69}{12}\right)}(440Hz) \quad (3)$$

In formula 3, we added ‘Hertz’ because we transform an adimensional number, the MIDI height information, into a physical quantity (number of oscillations per second). Conceptually, we are overall mapping a filtering rate into an oscillation rate. The rounding step is a choice allowing us to work with Western-tuned musical notes. However, we could have been running the whole analysis without it, also considering that other musical systems use different tunings, and contemporary music often uses microtones. From the point of view of sonification, the rounding step may emphasize data variations.

While we build up clusters on eGFR and, separately, on Hertz to compare them, we also examine additional information to characterize our sample. From the age of patients, we computed the spectral centroids. In this way, timbre can be balanced according to the patient’s age, creating a perceptual-equivalent effect. To compute the centroids, we converted age to Hertz with an inverse formula: $2^{-((y-69)/12)} * 440Hz$, to have an inverse relationship between age and luminosity of the sound (high-frequency component). That is, the younger the person, the brighter the sound. While dealing with timbre, we are more interested at mean values, thus we did not make specific hypothesis on tuning, and we skipped the rounding step. In next research, this method will be refined. In fact, in a few cases, since we are sonifying different data, we obtain values in Hertz of the spectral centroid (obtained from the age values) that are numerically lower than the mean Hertz value of the melody (obtained from the eGFR value), that is, of the fundamentals: this is not possible. This would require lower harmonics. A possible fix is the multiplication of the resulting number by a constant factor, to rise up all the values. A method to modify timbre independently by the pitch of a sound is discussed in [11].

2.3 The Clustering Techniques

In a former study [10], we had adopted a shape-similarity criterion [12], based on Fréchet distance [13]. Here, the greater dimension of the sample allows for a different trajectory-clustering technique, based on curve-parameter similarity, called *Traj* [7]. In this section, we summarize its main idea. Then, we sketch a new method for future research, specifically based on mathematical music theory [9].

2.3.1 The *Traj* method

The *Traj* method, developed by [7], allows one to classify trajectories in a longitudinal dataset. The method quanti-

fies how heterogeneous is a cohort concerning patterns of change, explaining how to use these patterns to group patients. The Traj method generates 24 measures for each given trajectory. The measures that appear as the most relevant ones for the considered problem are selected using factorial analysis. They constitute the starting point to compute trajectory clusters. The quantified information includes monotonicity degree, eventual abrupt changes and their direction, and the overall trajectory trend. For our case study, monotonicity, trend, and presence of sudden variations are important, corresponding to the response to the therapeutic treatment. Measures can be grouped into four main classes: measures of change, non-linearity, information of non-monotonicity and sudden changes, and early-versus-later change information. The detailed formulas are provided in the Appendix of [7].

2.3.2 The Fourier analysis

Fourier coefficients have been used to retrieve patterns of variation in genetics [14]. They have also been exploited for trajectory analysis, in the domain of Aeronautics [15]. As the main advantage, Fourier coefficients allow for a dimensional reduction of the examined problem. The development of Fourier coefficients for sound-signal processing is well-known. A bit less known is probably their application to characterize chords and scales in the realm of mathematical music theory [9].

Our idea is to merge all these aspects, sketching a new clustering method where:

- trajectories are first mapped to sound creating melodies;
- for each melody, Fourier coefficients are computed;
- melodies (and thus trajectories) are classified according to the position of their highest-valued coefficients.

In [9, section 5.2] (page 140 and *sequitur*), it is provided the formula to compute coefficients, a less common version of discrete Fourier transform (DFT):

$$c(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n e^{\frac{1}{6}i\pi(a_k - \frac{12kt}{n})}, \quad (4)$$

where n indicates the rank of the considered object; here, we have melodies of 4 notes: $n = 1, \dots, 4$, a_k is the k -th element of the melody, and t is the coefficient index $t = 1, \dots, 4$.

To apply this formula to our sonified trajectories, an additional step is needed. The formula considers musical notes *modulo 12*, that is, up to an octave. The information on precise pitches is thus forgotten, in favor of equivalence classes. To obtain pitch classes, we have to consider the MIDI values and subtract from each note the number ‘12’ until a number comprised between 0 and 11 is obtained. Then, we can apply formula 4.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Sonification output

As an example of the output, we list, as data strings, the Hertz values and note names of the melodies obtained by sonifying the first three patients of the considered sample. See Table 1 and Figure 1. The listed examples can be heard clicking [here](#). They have been created with software Sibelius. Clicking [here](#), it is possible to listen to the three sequences with electronically-modified spectral centroids. The effect has been obtained with software Melodyne. Figure 2 presents the superpositions of three melodies, and Figure 3 shows a single melody whose timbre has been adjusted (starting on a cello sound) to approximate the spectral centroid based on age.

patient	melody			
1	311.13	277.18	277.18	293.66
	E♭4	C#4	C#4	D4
2	246.94	293.66	277.18	329.63
	B3	D4	C#4	E4
3	293.66	311.13	349.23	415.30
	D4	E♭4	F4	A♭4

Table 1. Hertz values obtained for the first three patients (One note for each eGFR yearly measurement).

Figure 1. Melodies obtained from the first three patients. Click [here](#) to listen with an arbitrary flute rendition (centroid: approximately 1600 Hz), and [here](#) with an electronically-modified rendition (centroid: circa 800 Hz).

Figure 2. An example of superposition of melodies, with sonification of the eGFR trajectories of three patients. The first two patients belong to the same cluster (cl. 1), and present a parallel motion. The third one belongs to cluster 3. Click [here](#) for the audio file, with flute sounds.

3.2 Clustering results

3.2.1 Clustering of 256 patients with Traj

Figures 4 and 5, obtained applying Traj on eGFR and Hertz, respectively, indicate mean trajectories in each cluster. Clusters are numbered according to their numerosity.

Figure 3. The melody corresponding to a single eGFR trajectory. Clicking [here](#) it is possible to hear the audio, whose timbre has been electronically adjusted to approximate the age-based mean spectral centroid of 267.73 Hertz.

eGFR-based clusters have the following number of patients: 103, 64, and 89, respectively. Hertz-based clusters present the numerosity of 77, 170, and 9, respectively.

The eGFR-based mean trajectories (Figure 4) present a switch between patients of the first and second clusters, probably due to the change of drug after the baseline. The eGFR variation provides information on the status of controlled / uncontrolled DKD. We notice a cluster with improving disease (cl. 2), of stable disease (cl. 3) stuck on below-threshold filtering values, and a cluster with slightly-decreasing values, denoting a poorly-controlled DKD (cl. 1).

Figure 4. Clusters obtained applying Traj to original data.

Figure 5. Clusters obtained applying Traj to sonified data.

At a first glance, Hertz-based mean trajectories (Figure 5) seem to lose information on patients' switch. However, we notice an unexpected behavior of cluster 3 (the one with higher values), rising and then decreasing. The change happens in correspondence to the first follow-up, when patients have been tested after the change of drug. Thus, it looks like that the sonification procedure emphasized the switch occurred during measurements at the first follow-up. Cluster 2 in Figure 5, approximately corresponding to cluster 3 in Figure 4 (stable on bad filtering values), is not affected by any abrupt change. However,

the sonified information returns a slightly younger subset of patients, thus, with a more brilliant sound (higher spectral centroid).

Variations of disease progress can be evident in other variables before becoming manifest in the eGFR. It is the case, for example, of UACR (creatinine to albumine ratio) [16]. Here, let us consider age to gain further information (Table 2), with a closer eye on clusters 1-2 in Figure 4 and clusters 1-3 in Figure 5. Patients with an overall better disease progress are the younger ones. This information is confirmed by both techniques. However, the age gap amongst 1-2 in the first analysis and 1-3 in the second one is different. Patient distribution found with Hertz-based clustering presents a larger age gap. For a future analysis, it could be interesting to investigate the characteristics of DKD patients around 59 years old under therapy change and other variables. We will also test the effect of tuning choices on fine-graining cluster distribution.

method	cluster	mean age	mean centroid	mean eGFR	mean Hertz
original	1	64	587.33	76	353.89
	2	63	622.25	68	314.32
	3	71	392.00	48	222.62
sonified	1	64	587.33	74	344.58
	2	68	466.16	59	275.23
	3	59	783.99	73	339.95

Table 2. Overall comparison between mean values of clusters. Values for the 256 patients of the sample. Method 1: we compute clusters starting from the original values and then we mapped to sound the mean values in each cluster. Method 2: we first sonify the trajectories, and then we compute the clusters.

3.2.2 Clustering of 10 patients with Fourier

Applying the considered technique to the first ten patients of our dataset, we obtain notes in terms of pitch classes and the label of their higher two Fourier coefficients (Table 3). The cluster attribution is based on the label of the higher coefficient. In our example, we have a prevalence of c_2 (cl. 3), then c_4 (cl. 1), and then the others (cl. 2). To perform these computations, we coded a Jupyter program, which is available upon request. Table 3 contains a comparison with Traj-based clusters: interestingly, in 6 out of 10 patients, the classification is the same. In next research, such a comparison will involve all patients.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we proposed a sonification strategy to analyze medical longitudinal data. We applied our method to a dataset of 256 DKD patients, sonifying eGFR trajectories. We built clusters on original data and on sonified ones, discussing which characteristics are emphasized with the proposed strategy. Finally, we sketched a clustering approach derived by Fourier coefficients.

melody as pitch classes	higher coefficients	Fourier clusters	Traj clusters
3, 1, 1, 2	c_1, c_4	1	1
11, 1, 2, 4	c_3, c_4	2	2
2, 3, 5, 8	c_1, c_4	2	2
9, 8, 5, 7	c_2, c_3	3	3
6, 7, 5, 5	c_2, c_3	3	2
7, 8, 5, 3	c_2, c_3	3	1
0, 9, 9, 10	c_1, c_4	1 & 2	3
8, 8, 9, 11	c_1, c_1, c_2	3	3
8, 8, 8, 2	c_2, c_1, c_3	3	2
3, 1, 1, 2	c_1, c_4	1	1

Table 3. Results of Fourier-based method on ten patients, and comparison with Traj-based clusters.

A possible application of this method could lead to a new interface, where auditory clusters are automatically updated when data of a new patient are added, provided that they respect the time distribution of four different observations, from 1 to 4. Auditory detection of cluster variation would exploit human ear sensitivity in retrieving patterns, corresponding to patterns of behavior.

The interdisciplinary endeavor of precision medicine can profit from knowledge developed in deeply different field such as sonification and mathematical music theory. Such a multi-sensory perspective might help physicians retrieve hidden information, fostering new strategies toward individualized approaches to disease. Such an interdisciplinary challenge stresses the importance of collaboration between different research fields. And, ultimately, we hope that aesthetics, beauty, and music may help improve people’s lives.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Prof. Emmanuel Amiot for the insightful discussions on Fourier coefficients for musical analysis.

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